
JALALUDDIN MANGUBERDI - DEFENDER OF THE FATHERLAND

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Abstract: This article describes the life of Jalaluddin Manguberdi, his family, his brave struggles, the Mongol invasions, and the reasons for his escape to Movaraunnahr and Iran.

Keywords: Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Mongols, monument, Genghis Khan, Movarounnahr, Khorezmshahs

Jalaluddin Manguberdi (1199-1231) was the last ruler of the Khorezmshah state, known as a great commander and a national hero who fought against the Mongol invasions led by Genghis Khan in Central Asia at the beginning of the 13th century. His bravery and patriotism have been remembered for centuries among the peoples of Central Asia, and he has a special place in history as a true defender of the homeland.

Early Life and Family

Jalaluddin Manguberdi was born in 1199 in Gurlan, the capital of Khorezm. His father was Muhammad Khorezmshah, who ruled the kingdom of Khorezmshahs and made it a powerful state in Central Asia. The state of the Khorezmshahs was a large and powerful state that included Central Asia, Persia and the South Caucasus at that time. Khorezmshahs built a strong state and developed economically and culturally. But in 1218, when Khorezmshah Muhammad himself started to fight against the Mongol emperor Genghis Khan, wrong steps were taken that led to unpleasant results. As a result of the killing of Genghis Khan's merchants, the Mongols began to march against Khorezm. Jalaluddin Manguberdi received military and political

education from a young age and was prepared for public affairs. From a young age, he was distinguished by his courage and smart strategic thinking.

Manguberdi's Guerrilla Method and Tactics

The most important aspect of Jalaluddin Manguberdi's fight was his fighting strategy. He used the widespread "guerrilla" method in the fight against the Mongols. By using this method, he effectively fought against the large and organized army of the Mongols. Jalaluddin launched quick attacks with small groups against the powerful Mongol army, pursued the enemy troops in the dark and defeated them in several small battles. Also, Manguberdi knew the mountains and villages well, and through them he limited the Mongols' movements. In order to defeat them, he gathered his military team in a short period of time and organized special attacks. Through this method, Jalaluddin achieved great strategical gains over his opponents.

Diplomacy and Expansion of Alliances by Jalaluddin Manguberdi

Jalaluddin Manguberdi continued his struggle not only by his military forces, but also through diplomacy. He tried to get other countries as allies in the fight against the Mongols. For example, he sought help from Persia, Arabia, and other Central Asian countries, thereby increasing his political power.

The Period of Mongol Invasions and the Beginning of the Struggle

In 1219, the Mongols under the leadership of Genghis Khan launched an attack on the Khorezmshah state. Although Khorezmshah Muhammad initially preferred not to engage in open confrontation with the Mongols, when war became inevitable, he gathered an army to defend his country. During the Mongol invasion, Muhammad Khorezmshah was forced to flee and died soon after. At this time, the protection of the country was assigned to his son Jalaluddin Manguberdi.

Courageous Struggles of Jalaluddin against the Mongols

After the death of his father, Jalaluddin Manguberdi continued to fight to protect the state and stop the Mongols. One of his most famous battles is the battle against the troops led by Genghis Khan on the banks of the Amu Darya in 1221. In this battle, Jalaluddin Manguberdi showed his commanding skills and showed great

resistance on the battlefield. Jalaluddin, who was in a difficult situation in the battle, saved his life by jumping from the battlefield to Amudarya, and this became a symbol of his bravery.

Escape to Movarounnahr and Iran

After the conquest of Khorezm by the Mongols, Jalaluddin was forced to retreat towards Movarounnahr and Iran. He gathers supporters in these regions and tries to form a strong army against the Mongols. Although he won many battles, he could not completely liberate the territories due to the strong pressure of the Mongols.

Last Years and Death

Jalaluddin Manguberdi continued to fight against the Mongols even in the last years of his life. He died in 1231 in the Kurdistan regions of Iran in a battle with Mongol troops. With his death, the state of Khorezmshahs came to an end, and as a result of Genghis Khan's conquest, Mongol rule was established in Central Asia.

Jalaluddin Manguberdi Monument and Historical Place

Jalaluddin Manguberdi has gone down in history as a true hero of his people, a patriot and a freedom fighter. He fought for the freedom and independence of his country rather than personal interests. His bravery, heroism and patriotism are still remembered with respect among the peoples of Central Asia, and he is appreciated as a true defender of the homeland.

Many legends have been created about Jalaluddin

Manguberdi in historical sources and folklore, and many works have been written about his bravery for his country and people. His name has been forever preserved in history, and he is a glorious symbol of patriotism for the peoples.

The long-term history of the Khorezmshahs (1027-1231), ruled by the Anushtegin dynasty, is reflected in a number of works written by Muslim historians of that time. Based on them, it is possible to observe and analyze the reign of the last representative of this dynasty, the great general Jalaluddin Manguberdi, his heroic struggle against the Mongol invaders, and his activities on the borders of West Asia. In some sources and literature, his name is given as Mangburni. The works about Jalaluddin Manguberdi, created from the 13th century until now, amount to about 500

books. These works are conventionally divided into two periods: the first period - inscriptions written in the XIII-XVIII centuries; The second period can be divided into works created in the 18th-20th centuries. Most of the works created in the first period are written by Eastern historians and artists. They tell about Jalaluddin's life, activities and fate. Their battles against the Mongols are shown. Most of the authors of these works are people who saw, knew, heard about Jalaluddin, and were aware of his life ⁸⁹

Source historians, when talking about this period, emphasize more works such as "Siyрати Jalaluddin Mankburni" and "Tarihi Jahongusho". Because their authors, Shahabuddin al-Nasawi and Alauddin Atomalik Juvaini, saw the events in the picture with their own eyes, participated in them in some sense, and observed the events of history with as impartial an eye as possible. One of the most perfect sources about Jalaluddin's life and struggles is the work "Siirat us-sultan Jalaluddin Manguberdi (Manguburnu)" by Shahabeddin al-Nasawi. Nasavi, the owner of one of the castles in Nasso (Nisa) province, went to Iraq in 1224 on business and entered the service of Sultan Jalaluddin there. From then on, he became one of Jalaluddin's trusted servants and continued his Nasavi service under other rulers until 1231, that is, after the tragic death of Jalaluddin Manguberdi, and died in 1249 in the city of Aleppo. It is known from history books that Sultan Jalaluddin had another secretary besides Nasavi. His name is Khoja Nuriddin Zaydari Khurasani, and he wrote a biographical work in Persian called "Nafsat al-masdur fi futur zaman as-sudur va zaman su dur al-futur". Since the contents and author of this work are still unknown to our historians, some scholars call it Nasavi's work and see it as his second book, while others mistakenly interpret it as another name of "Siyрати Jalaluddin Mankburni".

The work "Siirat al-Sultan" is a work written in the style of memoirs and consists of an introduction and 108 chapters. Chapters I-IV of the work briefly describe the Mongol-Tatars, the origin of Genghis Khan, the rise of Genghis Khan and his subjugation of Mongolia and North China. Chapters V-XXII are devoted to

⁸⁹ Shihobuddin Muhammad an-Nasawi. Details of the life of Sultan Jalaluddin Manguberdi. Translation by Kamal Matyokubov. Tashkent: Uzbekistan-Yozuvchi. 1999. 7-b.

the life and work of Khorezmshah Alauddin Muhammad. From chapter XXIII to the end of the book, the Mongol invasion and Khorazmshah Alauddin Muhammad fled his country in disgrace, the life of Sultan Jalaluddin and his heroic struggle with the Mongol invaders, his activities in Azerbaijan and Iraq, and finally, the tragic the destruction is told. The chapters of "Siirat al-Sultan", especially the chapters covering the events of the years 1224-1231, have a unique and important scientific value, because the author's personal participation is visible in most of the events described.⁹⁰

Nasavi knew Jalaluddin Manguberdi closely, was directly involved in most of the events described in his work or relied on the reports of witnesses, and most importantly, he tried to speak objectively and truthfully, which increases the scientific value and level of reliability of the work. Nasavi started to finish his work in 1241, almost 10 years after Jalaluddin's death, and naturally he had the opportunity to express his opinion freely. The original Arabic text of Nasawi's "Sirat al-Sultan Jalaluddin Mangubur" and its translations into different languages have been published several times. Nasawi's work was written in Arabic and two incomplete copies arrived. One copy is kept in the National Library of France and the other in the British Museum. He published the Arabic text of the work in Octav U in 1891. This scientist also translated it into French and published it in 1895 (Paris, 1895. In PÉLOV, IIIe., ser, vol. IX-X). Based on this translation, in 1914-191 Yu. Ziya and A. Tawhid, in 1934 Najib Asim independently translated the work into Turkish, in 1945 by Muhammad Ali Nasikh from Arabic to Persian, and in 1953 based on the translation of O.U.da again into Arabic. translated by Hafiz Ahmad Hamdi. The work was partially published in Russian in 1850 and 1900. In particular, it was translated into Russian by the famous orientalist Z.M. Bunyotov and published twice (the second time with the Arabic text). The work was also published twice in Uzbek under the name "Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi" in the translation of K. Matyogubov.⁹¹

⁹⁰ Shihobuddin Muhammad an-Nasawi. Sultan Details of the life of Jalaluddin Manguberdi. Translation by Kamal Matyokubov. Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2006.

⁹¹ Ismat Ochilov. Description of Jaloliddin Manguberdi in written sources// "Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal – (4) IV/2020. 64-b.

In his work, Nasavi describes the figure of the general Sultan Jalaluddin as follows: "He (Jalaluddin) came from Karacha, was of medium height, according to his speech and expressions, he spoke Turkish, but he also spoke Persian. As for his bravery he was the lion among lions, the bravest of all skilful riders. He had a gentle nature and never got angry or cursed. He takes himself seriously, but also influenced the nature of the period of rebellions he faced. He strives to improve the lives of citizens, but he was forced to use force because he ruled in a time of depression. The words "Help is only from Allah" were written on his labels".⁹²

In "Siirat al-Sultan" Nasavi lived in the kingdom of Khorezm, Movarounnahr, Khorasan, India, Iran, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Georgia from 1218 to 1231. The events that took place, the activities of Khorezmshah Alauddin Muhammad and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, the invasion of Genghis Khan are told. The details of the events presented in the work are narrated by a historian standing in the position of the Khorezmshahs. Nasavi, unlike other historians of other times, is concerned with the internal and external life of the Khorezmshah state, the Turkon Khatun and its place in the life of the country, the reasons for the decline of the kingdom, the treachery of the nomadic Turkic tribes (especially the Kipchaks and the Turkon Khotun clan), the Caliph of Baghdad The two-faced policy, Jalaluddin's internal and foreign policy (relations with the Ismailis, the Ayyubids, and the Hurrians), the reasons and consequences of his campaigns are explained and interpreted on a new basis.⁹³

According to the information of the work, Jalaluddin Manguberdi was in a difficult time, Movarounnahr was drawn into the war, most of the country was conquered by the Mongols, the army of Khorezmshahs was destroyed, some of the emirs were traitors, and the rest were their own. appeared on the stage of history at a time when the sultan left the country to fend for himself, and there was mutual confusion and danger.

⁹²Nasir Muhammad. Mysterious Jewels. Historical Etudes. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2016.9-b.

⁹³Shihobuddin Muhammad al-Nasawi. Details of the life of Sultan Jalaluddin Manguberdi. Translation by Kamal Matyokubov. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2006.

In such a difficult situation, Jalaluddin fought for the homeland and the will of the people and fought against the Mongols for 11 years. He fought against the Mongols 14 times and won 13 of them.⁹⁴

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